

SUBSTANTIATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTRAOPERATIVE CLOSURE OF WOUND DEFECTS OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE HARD PALATE WITH AN ADHESIVE INSULATING BANDAGE

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Annotation: The optimal treatment of postoperative mucosal defects and the lack of tissue volume around the opening of the hard palate and the accumulated practical experience of the process of repair tissue regeneration in maxillofacial surgery. A feature of wound healing in the oral cavity is the presence of a diverse microflora, constant mechanical, thermal and chemical loads on the tissues of this localization and high specificity of their histological structure, which leads to the formation of deformed scar tissue and often changes in the architecture of the palate. Wound defects of the mucosa of the hard palate are treated today under protective plates, gauze swabs or open methods [1]. The use of these methods for the treatment of wound defects of the mucosa of the hard palate does not always allow to restore structural changes in the damaged tissue and restore lost functions [2]. In addition, the recovery period from postoperative wounds of the palate is very painful and uncomfortable for the patient, so it is necessary to find ways to treat such defects of the mucosa of the hard palate and optimize the course of the wound process [3]. The search for methods and materials continues, the use of which can reduce the negative effects of the postoperative period. Tissue adhesives based on blood derivatives (fibrin and protein-aldehyde adhesives) are widely used in various fields of medicine. Their advantages include complete recombination within a few weeks, biocompatibility with body tissues and the ability to accelerate wound healing [4-6]. They have adhesive properties similar to those of a normal blood clot, ensuring a firm fixation of tissues and closure of the wound surface. Adhesives

based on blood derivatives contribute to the creation of optimal conditions for wound surface treatment, since fibrin attracts inflammatory cells to the wound, which eliminate dead tissue, and also secretes cytokines that stimulate the production of fibroblasts and the formation of connective tissue [7]. The use of existing tissue adhesives significantly improves the aesthetic quality of postoperative scars, so they are widely used in plastic surgery. On the basis of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Transfusion and Medical Biotechnology, an adhesive based on blood derivatives (protein-aldehyde sealing) - surgical adhesive "Albucard" was developed. The described properties of this sealant allow it to be used as an adhesive insulating dressing for the treatment of wound defects of the mucosa of the hard palate. An important role is played by studies in laboratory animals on the effectiveness of the treatment of this pathology by adhesive insulating dressings in comparison with traditional methods.

The aim of the study was: to experimentally evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment of wound defects of the hard palate mucosa by adhesive insulating dressings using morphological methods in comparison with open treatment of the wound process.

Materials and Methods: The experiments were carried out on the basis of the laboratory of the Samarkand State Medical University under standard vivarium conditions. The experimental group consisted of 24 small chinchilla rabbits weighing 3,500. 500 g. Before the experiments, the appearance and behavior of the animals, the physiological color of the visual mucosa were evaluated, and control measurements were made. Under general anesthesia (30 mg / kg sodium thiopental, intravenously), two symmetrical lesions of round shape, defects 0. The thickness of the bone mucosa with an area of 5 cm² modeled the entire hard palate. One wound surface in the area of thousand hard palate was sealed with an adhesive insulating dressing (surgical adhesive "Albucard" produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan) (experimental side), the other was corrected in an open way – traditional technology

(comparison side). Experimental treatment of wounds under gauze swabs and protective plates, traditionally used in medicine, is not carried out, since it is difficult to heal in the mouth of rabbits, and the possibility of normal food intake of animals is also excluded. Animals were kept according to the standards of their individual habitat. [8] The lighting mode corresponds to the level of daytime low lighting at the geographical intensity of Minsk ($53^{\circ} 54' n$). Air temperature was kept in the range of $18-25^{\circ} C$ and relative humidity of 50-70%. Air temperature and humidity were recorded daily. Animals were fed gently in the amounts prescribed by current regulations, the water regime was free. On the first day, animals were constantly monitored for 8 hours a day. For visual assessment of the progress of the treatment, digital images of the wound surface were taken at certain time intervals of 0, 7, 14 and 21 days after the operation, the wound area was described accordingly in Image JV5B (National Institute of Health, USA), and the wound healing rate was calculated according to the following formula: where sh is the initial area of the wound and C is the final area/measurement. It was a great experience. The experimental animals were taken from the experiment by injection of sodium barbital (50 mg/kg, intravenous), administered on the 7th, 14th and 21st days of the study, according to the study design. The days of the postoperative period are another sample for histological examination of the material. The tissue with the lesion was fixed for 24 hours in a 10% formalin solution buffered by lily. Then, a histopathological resection was performed: the first incision was 5 mm from the edge of the wound or scar, the second - 15 mm, the third - 25 mm, the fourth - 35 mm, the fifth - 45 mm. Segments with a thickness of 4-5 μm were made from the blocks on a microtome, the latter were stained with hematoxylin and eosin, and histological examination according to Van Giessen was performed according to standard methods.

Results and discussion: As a result of an experimental study carried out to study the effectiveness of the treatment of wound defects of the hard palatal mucosa

with adhesive insulating dressings in comparison with the open treatment of the wound process, the following data were obtained. On the 7th day after the operation, visual assessment of the wound defect, where the wound was openly healed (traditional technique), showed that the area of the wound defect was smaller than the original wound . Due to the massive formation of granulation tissue along the edges of the defect . When using adhesive insulating dressings during this study period, the area of the wound defect decreased compared to the initial lesion, since the glue mass along the edges of the wound was gradually replaced by a defect of granulation tissue, but this was less significant in the comparative group. The data of histological examination confirm the results of the visual assessment. In biopsies of the mucosa of the hard palate of rabbits, where open therapy is used, several fragmented leukocytes are formed in the adjacent parts of the mucosa, and extensive secretory inflammation, including adipose tissue, is formed with a significant number of fragmented leukocytes inherent in the processes of granular tissue, indicating the active process of the inflammatory stage of the lesion process. In contrast to lesions with treatment without adhesive tape, foreign bodies of plant origin (food debris) are found in the cellular debris and in the inflammatory areas, and in lesions with its use, cellular debris is found in the cellular debris and in the inflammatory areas. In the intact submucosa, at the border with the fibrinoid change zone, there is a proliferation of fibroblasts with small capillary vessels, which determines the formation of a granular tissue with a uniform eosinophilic adhesive mass on the cell surface and in its interior . On the 14th. The day after the operation, due to the secondary load (open wound management) and complete epithelialization under the adhesive separation tape, there is still no wound healing area, but in the group with open wound management, the tendency to connect the edges of the wound is more pronounced . The area of the wound defect was significantly reduced compared to the initial lesions in both groups. Histological examination of the mucosal preparations shows that during this period of

examination, the wound is healed with secondary stress (open wound management), showing the purification of the wound defect from cellular debris and their replacement, the development of granular tissue with a large inflammatory infiltrate, the formation of a secretory inflammation that persists in the adjacent parts of the subcutaneous layer. In the area of inflammation, foreign bodies of plant origin are found. When examining biopsies of the mucosa under the adhesive, a pronounced absorption of cellular debris is detected by the formation of a border zone of microflora and macrophages on the border with the underlying tissue, which can be considered an indicator of the initial stage of fecal matter. In the area of frontier inflammation, there is a pronounced proliferation of small blood vessels, such as fibroblasts and capillaries, granulation and active formation of connective tissue, indicating a period of active regeneration in the deep sclerotic areas . Visual evaluation on the 21st day resulted in the healing of all postoperative defects with secondary exposure to scar tissue formation (see table). However, in contrast to the open wound therapy samples, in which the wound surface is closed faster and a rough scar is formed, when using adhesive tape in the group, the scar is manifested by a narrow band of connective tissue, which minimally deforms the hard palate. On the 21st day after surgery, during histological examination, the area heals openly, integrated epithelial return and treatment of the wound defect with a recorded scar. The obvious difference between wound healing under a dressing and open wound healing is due to tissue adhesive properties that stimulate fibroblast production and connective tissue formation, which contributes to the organization of a delicate aesthetic scar. Analysis of morphological study data shows the advantage of using insulating adhesive tape (surgical adhesive "Albucard") over surface treatment of the open mouth wound cavity. It necrosis and contouring at the borders of relatively intact tissue is represented by the formation of inflammatory areas, followed by resorption of cellular debris and wound. Histological evaluation of postoperative lesions on the 7th and 14th days of pregnancy. The day after

closure, the greatest inflammatory and tissue reaction was observed with open wound surface management, which was most pronounced on the 7th day. Also, the protection of insulating adhesive tape made of surgical adhesive "Albucard" was used as a wound dressing to isolate the wound surface from mechanical and chemical irritants in the oral cavity for a long time. Visual evaluation on the 21st day showed that all postoperative defects had healed with secondary exposure to scar tissue formation. With the open method of treating the wound surface, more pronounced traces of the hard palate were observed. According to the obtained critical values ($P = 0.005$ and $p = 0.0001$, respectively), significant differences were observed in comparison with the open wound healing kinetics in the presence of adhesive tape at 7 and 14 days, respectively. At 21 days, the difference in wound healing is negligible ($P = 0.691$). It should be noted that in both groups at 21 days, it was statistically proven that the wound defect heals with the restoration of the connective epithelium, while in the group with the dressing, a scar is formed. A comparison of experimental methods for the treatment of postoperative superficial lesions of the mucosa of the hard palate, made within the framework of this work, shows that when the wound is closed with adhesive tape, the shape of the wound gradually changes due to the gradual replacement of the blood clot. It prevents the overgrowth of tissue particles, protects the wound from the influence of positive factors of the oral cavity, thereby enhancing the aesthetic quality of the postoperative scar.

Conclusions: 1. Compared with open treatment of the wound process, the use of insulated adhesive tape reduces the appearance of inflammatory processes in the areas adjacent to the wound and contributes to a more favorable process in the postoperative period. 2. Sealing the wound surface after surgery with insulating tape provides long-term protection of the wound from the influence of positive elements of the oral cavity and enhances the aesthetics of the postoperative scar. 3. Comparing the dynamics of healing in pairs, the data prove that at 21 days the

wound defect was corrected by restoring the underlying epithelium in both groups, although scarring was observed, which was less evident in the group with the use of adhesive tape.

Literature:

1. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. ОСНОВЫ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕЙ ВРАЧЕБНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

2. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL MEDICAL PRACTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE DENTAL CARE //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

3. Astanovich A. D. A. et al. The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 235-241.

4. Alimjanovich R. J., Astanovich A. A. СОВЕРШЕНТСТВО ВАНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕЕ КАЧЕСТВА //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.

5. Ортикова Н. Глобализация биоэтики в период пандемии COVID-19 //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 677-682.

6. Ортикова Н. Влияние психоэмоционального напряжения детей на состояние здоровья полости рта //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 7/S. – С. 328-333.

7. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ

СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРИЕМА ПАЦИЕНТОВ ДЕТСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 554.

8. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 181-189.

9. Fakhridin C., Shokhrub S., Nilufar I. ENDOKANAL PIN-KONSTRUKSIYALARNI ISHLATISHDA ASORATLAR VA XATOLAR TAHLILI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.

10. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF ORAL INFECTIONS IN DENTURE WEARERS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 4.

11. Xusanovich C. F. COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 127-133.

12. Xusanovich C. F. et al. PROSTHETICS A COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS BASED ON IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 122-126.

13. Sevinch E., Zarafruz B. ETIOLOGICAL TREATMENT FEATURES INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASE //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 03. – С. 241-246.

14. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF COPD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS //European International Journal of

Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 363-368.

15. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY THE EFFECT OF HYGIENIC CARE ON THE MICROBIAL LANDSCAPE OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PATIENTS USING COMBINED SPLINTING STRUCTURES WITH MODERATE PERIODONTITIS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 50-55.

16. Sevinch E., Qobilovna B. Z. A STUDY ON THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF ORAL ORGAN TISSUES DURING THE USE OF NON-REMOVABLE ORTHODONTIC STRUCTURES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 03. – C. 247-253.

17. Shaximardonova E. S., Kobilovna B. Z. RED LICHEN PLANUS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA AND ITS CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF A PATIENT WITH, ASSOCIATED WITH THE EPSTEIN—BARR VIRUS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 01. – C. 272-279.

18. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY OF CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY IN ENDOCRINE DISEASES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 357-362.

19. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. SMARTBURS II—A REVIEW OF THE ADVANTAGES OF SMART BOR //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 56-60.